

ANALYSIS OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS FOR THE REPAIR OF HIGH-STRENGTH FLOORS IN INDUSTRIAL AND RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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The installation and repair of high-strength floors in industrial and civil buildings is one of the priorities in scientific research. An analysis of organizational and technological solutions for the repair of high-strength floors in industrial and civil buildings was carried out, as presented by the American Concrete Institute (ACI) and the Portland Cement Association (PCA).

Crack repair is performed by injecting or gravity feeding a semi-rigid, low-viscosity filler into a cleaned crack, taking into account the structural integrity of the floor. Restoration of wear resistance involves determining the depth of low-quality mixture. Diamond polishing may be required to remove a thin fragile surface layer.

Repair of concrete delamination. The causes of surface delamination of concrete floors are often the result of finishing operations or inadequate curing of the concrete. The removal of damaged layers is carried out until the proper air-void structure and concrete strength are achieved. Under conditions of significant temperature fluctuations, the surface material must have a thermal expansion coefficient consistent with that of the concrete floor. Restoration of surface wear resistance of concrete through the use of aggregates must meet all requirements when placing concrete floors. Two-layer concretes that meet all filling requirements should be used. Fillers should be used that contain no harmful impurities or contain them in minimal amounts. Curing practices must be carried out, such as maintaining moisture and temperature regimes, covering with polyethylene film, or wet burlap immediately after finishing. Curing should last at least 7 days, since moist curing can significantly reduce or eliminate future surface scaling. For alkali-silica reactions, the internal relative humidity must be at least 80%. When installing concrete floors on waterproofing coatings, the prolonged presence of cement laitance on the surface must be taken into account. When designing repair works for high-strength floors, maximum consideration must be given to survey data on the technical condition of existing structures, as well as strict adherence to technological requirements for the removal of defective areas and preparation for repair.

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